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OF RESULT

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Abstract:- Generally, man thinks for god at old age when he hears the footsteps of death. He becomes afraid when he realizes that the death is imminent. Tear rolls down through his pale cheeks when death drags him. He discovers that everybody and everything will exist after his death. Only he will not exist. He cannot imagine it. He cannot bear this pain. This is inevitable destiny. This is the ultimate result of all human being.

Keywords: - Result, consequence, outcome, item of information, quantity, formula

INTRODUCTION

Creative writing is based more on manifestation rather than on expression. It does not inform, rather it reveals. So it bears no reference. The best creative writing is critical, and the best critical writing is creative. This article is an outcome of thinking about creative writing meant for a general readership. As such, I have adopted a free style methodology so that everyone can enjoy the pleasure of reading. As you might know, Francis Bacon (1561-1626), the immortal essayist, wrote many essays namely 'Of Love', 'Of Friendship', 'Of Ambition', 'Of Studies', and so on. The multiple-minded genius correctly pointed out that all the words of the dictionary can be used as themes for essays. But little has been done since his death to continue or finish his monumental task. Bacon's unique individual style of presentation ignited my imagination and encouraged me to write creative essays as a method of relieving a wide range of emotions through catharsis.

ARTICLE

Result is a thing that is caused or produced by something else. For example: His broken leg is

the direct result of his own carelessness.

It is a consequence or outcome. For example: The tower collapsed as a result of safety violations.

It is an item of information obtained by experiment or some other scientific method.

It is a quantity or formula obtained by calculation. For example: The results are evaluated by the researcher.

They say, "Life is not a bed of roses". A judicious person knows that if the arrow is thrown from the bow it cannot be returned back. As such the proverb goes, "Look before you leap". It is a caution against haughtiness. It insists a person to judge before doing anything. It is an advice to a novice or an inexperienced person to be careful regarding hard reality. It enables a person to remain in safe and comfort zone which is the prime objective of any sensible person.

There are two types of persons. The first category thinks for result always. The second category thinks never. He is whimsical in nature. He is fickle-minded. He does whatever he thinks. Such a restless person falls down and breaks his crown as described in nursery rhymes.

In real life result or outcome is all and everything. It signifies either rise or downfall. Sometimes it defines tie i.e., fifty- fifty or no profit no loss or draw.

Result is mundane. Indifference is divine. To a mundane person result is the only tool to ascertain the social

status. A mundane person considers a divine person simply as a first class callous. He laughs at him. He cannot judge the strategy of the divine soul. He cannot realize that how will the divine person will exist? To his dismay he notices that the divine soul yet exists.

A divine person remains far from the profit and loss account of life. He loves all. He hates none and never. He surrenders completely to the Almighty God. Belief is his only single agenda. He is fully dependent on the mercy of god for salvation. In that respect he is not independent. He is a devotee. He accepts both weal and woe of life with a smiling face. He perceives that all are God's whims. God is the controller of both theist and atheist as well. God loves them both. He realizes the blessings of the super power in each and every footstep.

Criminal is identified from the clue thus left quite in his unaware. In case of rape rapist is identified by DNA test. In case of gang rape liability is imposed upon the culprit whose sperm is responsible for the pregnancy though all persons thus involved enjoyed equally and are equally responsible for the offence. Unfortunately one person becomes the victim. Obviously, here master mind of the incidence gets severe punishment.

A good student always is interested to know the result of the examination. In contrast a bad student wants not to know it. Though he knows regarding his confirmed failure yet he wants not to be officially confirmed after result out of the examination. He prays to the god that result does not come out publicly.

A honeymoon couple wants to know the result of sexual intercourse i.e., pregnancy. They celebrate it if the wife becomes pregnant. The would be parents are eager to see the face of the newly born babe. With much enthusiasm they try to discover the resemblance of the new face either of father or mother. It is an emotional venture.

In contrast the partners of live together consider pregnancy as a bondage which they want not at all and hate. They consider live together as simply as stay together for the time being. There is no commitment for permanent relation. To them pregnancy i.e., bondage means hurdle for free sexual enjoyment. It is harassment.

In a conservative society virgin mother faces social dogma. In patriarchal society loss of virginity culminates either into honour killing or death or suicide. Yet the lovers love knowing even the result of such risky game. To them no risk no gain implies high risk high gain. To such an emotionally charged soul love for one day is far better than thousand years without any love.

In fact the relation in live together is temporary likely to be permanent. The relation depends on the likeness of the partners together. The relation cannot exist singly. It is a bi-partite issue seldom a one-sided game. If the partners both are serious then the relation becomes permanent. If either or both the partners are moody and the relation vacillates always then the result suffers from uncertainty. This is equally true in every sphere of life. Man experiences it from cradle to coffin.

The result of live together is illegal children. The homes for orphans are overcrowded by these human babes. They become prodigal being deprived from mother's affection. They are headache of the society thereby national at large. Thus live together is not illegal, it is immoral.

Permanency depends on the likeness of the big boss. The boss sometimes likes. Sometimes he likes not. He likes if he likes. He likes not if he likes not. He may accept someone or something in the morning. He may reject that very person or that very thing in the evening or early of that very day without showing any cause. Thus his mood and motive are gloriously so uncertain. He feels no urge to give explanation to anybody. He possesses thereby enjoys super power or protection.

The boss likes nepotism. He is kind. He accepts cash. Between cash or kind he prefers cash more. He is so kind that he accepts only cash. He opts for cash. Cash is noted for its liquidity which is not possible in being kind. Boss knows the result of acceptance of cash or kind.

Someone is fully responsible for any result. He is singularly liable. Someone is half responsible. He is jointly responsible with equal weightage. Someone is partly responsible. He is partially responsible with defined onus. Thus responsibilities are of various types depending on degrees and dimensions of the deeds thus performed.

Someone is anxious for result. Someone is not at all. A good student is never anxious for his result. He is confident for his good result. He is simply curious to know it. He hopes for the good always. Always good or always bad is impossible. Life is a cock-tail of both. If he fails then he becomes very upset. He loses interest of life. He does not want to exist more. Such a serious person takes life very seriously. He may commit suicide. He becomes a pessimist.

A bad student always fails in the examination. He knows that his failure is sure and certain. He is not anxious for his result. In this regard he is equal to good student. The former is confident for his success and the latter one is certain for his utter failure.

Problem lies with the mediocre students. Such a student can answer the easy questions only. If the questions are difficult then they submit blank answer script. As such fate of the mediocre student depends on the nature of the questions set in the examination.

Some students depend on presumption. They practice omission. They think that, generally, in the examination repetition of questions of the previous year is not done. So they avoid those topics. If questions on those topics do

not appear then they get relief. In case of repetition their failure is confirmed. However, difficult questions of both known and unknown topics are identical to an inattentive student.

Study demands thinking and imagination. To grasp any lesson both are must. Thinking and imagination are alias and akin to physical pain. Very few can bear that pain. This answers why successful persons are numbered. Results of most of the persons are substandard or below standard. They are lay men and large in numbers. They are laborers.

Human resource is very important for any country. Educated mass is a prize thereby blessing to a nation. Uneducated or illiterate mass is a punishment thereby curse. Un-skilled laborers are abundant in a poor nation. There is scarcity of skilled laborer and experts not in poor or undeveloped nations rather it is true around the world. Consistent good academic result gives birth to experts. This consistency is not a matter of joke.

An optimist always sees the positive side of life. He preaches that, "Don't commit suicide since life has its sweet side too". He always thinks for sunrise. He never thinks for sunset. If someone says about sunset then this sincere optimist contends that every sunset guarantees another sun rise in the morning of the very next day. Thus the result of sun set is sun rise. Here lies the uniqueness of sun rise rather than unique sun set.

Result is all and everything. A tree is known by its fruits. Similarly, success reveals the charisma of someone. They say nothing succeeds like success. Success has no substitute. Success itself is its substitute. The proverb goes, "All is well that ends well". It means man will work and save for the old days. An old man cannot work further to maintain his livelihood. Here savings saves him.

Savings is a classical success. It is an art. Debt is an artistic failure. He who does not or cannot save dies unfed at old age. All cannot save. Someone does not save due to lavish expenditure. It is his curse. He hears none. As a result he does not get help in his rainy days for his past haughtiness. He realizes that he has committed Himalayan blunder in his early days. In that belated period of life he has nothing to do except repentance and mourning. If luck favours then only a Good Samaritan appears to rescue him.

A lay person always thinks for result. He has to decide future steps depending upon present result. None helps in danger is his bitter experience. He has to solve alone the problems as are faced with thereby save him. It is hard reality. As such he is alert for his deeds.

In contrast a pious soul never thinks for result. The devotee thinks that he has right upon duty never on its result which is the concern of the Almighty God. The divine soul is tuned in such a unique way which is diagonally opposite to mundane decision of the lay person.

Mundane attraction is very powerful. Very few people can overcome that attraction and can respond to the divine

call. Some communities are pious. Their children are guided accordingly. They practice it. They preach it. It is their orientation. Good culture helps to nurture it. Divine souls spread it.

CONCLUSION

Generally, man thinks for god at old age when he hears the footsteps of death. He becomes afraid when he realizes that the death is imminent. Tear rolls down through his pale cheeks when death drags him. He discovers that everybody and everything will exist after his death. Only he will not exist. He cannot imagine it. He cannot bear this pain. This is inevitable destiny. This is the ultimate result of all human being.

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They say and hearsay